

THE RESULTS OF PRELIMINARY STUDIES OF UZBEKISTAN AND CHINESE BREEDS OF SILKWORM *BOMBYX MORI L*

B.U. Nasirillaev¹, S.Kh. Khudjamatov¹, Wang Yongqiang², Du Xin²

Scientific Research Institute of Sericulture, Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent¹

Institute of Sericulture and Tea, Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Hangzhou, China²

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Abstract. *The importance of breeds and hybrids is very great for obtaining high and high-quality yields of cocoons of Bombyx mori L. silkworm. The article examines the results of preliminary studies conducted jointly by breeders from the Republic of Uzbekistan and the People's Republic of China. During the research, local hybrids and hybrids with several genotypes, imported from China, were compared and key biological indicators identified. It should be noted separately that the hatchability of eggs in industrial silkworm hybrids marked as Q, K and M ranged from 92.3% to 99.3%, larvae viability ranged from 91.8 to 97.8%, and the cocoon weight was 1.74–1.98 g. It was established that the percent cocoon shell in new hybrids was 21.8–22.4%, which fully meets production requirements.*

Keywords: *silkworm, hybrid, cocoon, larva, percent cocoon shell, local hybrid, viability.*

Introduction. In Uzbekistan, over the past 3-4 years, there has been a tendency towards an increase in cocoon production volumes. The production of cocoons during the summer and autumn seasons also contributes to these changes. Despite some progress, we face serious challenges in increasing cocoon yields and producing high-quality silk in our country. In addition, there are sufficient difficulties in creating new plantations of mulberry high-yielding varieties and in the control of various diseases of mulberry and silkworm. The infrastructure of sericulture and workforce in Uzbekistan allow for repeated silkworm breeding both in summer and autumn. However, there are not enough suitable breeds, hybrids and mulberry varieties, as well as agricultural technologies. By creating new breeds, hybrids and mulberry varieties together with Chinese scientists, and by rationally using mulberry plantations, our republic has the potential to produce an additional 3-4 thousand tons of cocoons. By effectively using the potential of Chinese scientists and experts, it is possible to further increase the production of cocoons and high-quality silk.

Up to the present time, in our republic, in addition to local silkworm breeds, has been used the practice of obtaining industrial seeds from elite Chinese seeds of unknown origin, the characteristics and suitability of which for Uzbekistan have not been substantiated. As a result, the cocoon yield and its quality indicators do not meet the required level. As a result, it is impossible to produce silk products that meet the demand of enterprises in China, the world's largest silk importer. If the quality of silk products produced in Uzbekistan meets the requirements of Chinese enterprises, then opportunities will be created for exporting more than 2-2.5 thousand tons of raw silk, skeins of silk filament and other silk products from Uzbekistan to this country per year.

Currently, in countries with developed sericulture, research is being conducted to create breeds and hybrids with high productivity and resistance to diseases. Indian researchers Raje Urs S., Basavaraja H.K., Suresh Kumar N., Kalpana G.V., Mal Reddy N. [1] obtained complex hybrids by double crossing of silkworms. For example, as a result of crossing the bivoltine varieties Sfp x

rb and monovoltine 13a x 137 according to this scheme, the combination (Sfp.rb x 13a137) x (Sfp.137 x Rb.13a) was created, high-yielding hybrids of which are used on an industrial scale.

Bulgarian scientists are also conducting extensive research in this direction. Guncheva R. [2] studied 8 dihybrid and 10 trihybrid parental lines with the aim of obtaining high-yielding hybrid combinations with high metric indicators from sex-limited systems. The work of Bulgarian scientists differs from studies of Indian researchers in that they worked with sex-limited breeds.

Chinese scientists Cheng, L., Zhao, H., Huang, H., Li, B., Li, R. K. Y., Feng, X.-Q. & Dai, F. [3]; Hao, Z., Long, D., Zhang, Y., Umuhoza, D., Dai, J., Xua, Z., Zhang, G., Meng, W., Xiang, Z. & Zhao, A. [4] are conducting research on obtaining male hybrid offspring by exposure to various physical rays in order to create economical and fine silk-producing silkworm breeds. They believe that at present time the use of male hybrids in production is more economically profitable. In this case, the larvae consume less food, mount cocoons in a short time, and the cocoon is uniform in caliber, producing silk that meets the 6A requirement.

Xue-Yang Wang, Kang-Hui Wu, Hui-Lin Pang, Ping-Zhen Xu, Mu-Wang Li, Guo-Zheng Zhang [5] at Jiangsu University of Science and Biotechnology and the Silkworm Biotechnology Laboratory in China are conducting research to identify genes resistant to viral diseases in silkworm chromosomes and to create breeds with high viability.

Ai Junwen, Sima Yanghu, He Xingjian, Xue Hong, Tang Yun, Zheng Ying, Liu Yong [6] analyzed various factors affecting cocoon productivity and silk quality of a new industrial hybrid silkworm. From 2015 to 2019, laboratory tests were conducted on newly created silkworm hybrids for inclusion in the state register. Taking into account the variation coefficients of the Jin Xiu x Xiao Xiang breeds, these breeds were compared in terms of the number of healthy eggs in a laying with larvae viability, the yield of cocoons and the length of silk filature, and in terms of stability they were compared with the control hybrid Qiufeng x Baiyu, while the experimental hybrids exceeded the control hybrid in terms of the number of eggs by 12.07%.

Wang P., Zhao Q., Qiu Z., Bi S., Wang W., Wu M., Chen A., Xia D., He X., Tang S., Li M., Zhang G., Shen X. [7] conducted studies to obtain mutants producing pigment in individuals with purple coloration, which occurs in the population of common silkworm breeds 932VR and 0223JH. As a result of the study, a number of scientific and theoretical foundations for fundamental research were identified.

Scientists have long been interested in silkworms, which quickly mount cocoons. In particular, in Uzbekistan, as a result of the selection work of N.V. Shurshchikova [8] on silkworm breeds that mature quickly and yield early, SANIISH 17 and SANIISH 21 breeds were obtained.

Indian scientists have conducted research to study the biology of Mcon-1 silkworm breed in laboratory conditions. The third stage of embryonic development of eggs, that is the hatching period, was 8.6 days, the larval period of caterpillars was 23.7 days, the cocoon mounting of larvae was 2.3 days, the pupal period was 10 days, and the moth period was 4.6–5.9 days. It was also found that female larvae live longer than males. The sex ratio throughout the larvae's life cycle was 1:1.3 [9].

Scientists K. Sashindran nari, Miao yun-gen, S. Niral Kumar [10] (2005) from Mysore Institute in India and Zhejiang University in China recommended the use of phytoecdysteroids to accelerate the development and metabolism of silkworms. In this study, Chinese hybrids of the famous Xinhang x Keming silkworm were exposed to phytoecdysteroids for two different periods of time using the mulberry breed «Hu Sang 197». In this case, larvae were fed with mulberry

leaves treated with a 2 μ M solution at 14, 48 and 72 h of their fifth instar. As a result, this affected the duration of the larval stage, the duration of growth and the properties of the cocoon mounting. The intensity of this substance effect depends on the time of application, and all biological and technological indicators of larvae, treated for 48 hours, improve. When applied for 72 hours, a negative effect on these parameters was observed. At the same time, the duration of the larval period of the caterpillars was reduced by 24 hours.

B.K.Kariappa, R.K.Rajan [11] developed various selection strategies for breeding monovoltine breeds and hybrids of silkworm. As a result, they managed to create polyvoltine silkworm breeds with high silk yield, resistance to diseases and high filament quality.

In Uzbekistan, B.U. Nasirillaev [12] in his research aimed at obtaining industrial hybrids with high technological indicators, by crossing the selection systems Line 27 and Line 28 of silkworm, obtained direct and reciprocal hybrids with superior technological indicators.

Scientists from Islom Azad University Reza Neshagaran Hemmatabadia, Alireza Seidavib, Shahabodin Gharahveysic [13] stated about the importance of observing heredity, variability and combination of one trait with another of objects taken for selection, when creating highly productive silkworm breeds.

Of course, it has already been explained that the role of hereditary variability, phenotypic and genotypic correlation is of great importance in the creation of new breeds.

Sahan U., Sozcu A., Gunduz M. [14] conducted research on the quantitative characteristics of Japanese and Chinese silkworm breeds. Researchers have proven that there is a correlation in the range $r=0.596-0.926$ between the larvae mass of these species, the mass of the cocoon and its shell.

Based on the analysis of the scientific works presented below, it can be concluded that an in-depth study of the economic and biological characteristics of the silkworm as a selection trait, the identification and selection of the most rapidly developing and metabolically active genotypes in the population of local pure breeds and new selection systems are of great importance in the creation of new breeds and hybrids.

Methods and techniques of research. Selection experiments were conducted in specialized worm farms of the laboratory "Breeding of silkworms" of the Research Institute of Sericulture in optimal hygrothermal conditions and in compliance with the "Basic methodological rules for breeding silkworms". Experimental hybrid populations were grown on uniform quality mulberry leaves delivered from the mulberry plantations of the unitary enterprise "Tutchilik Experimental Farm".

During the study, industrial hybrids were imported from China. The hybrids were hatched under identical hygrothermal conditions, the hatching rates were determined, and the caterpillars were counted and grown in 3 replicates (250 individuals each) from each breed and hybrid.

The following key economic indicators were identified:

- egg hatchability, %;
- larvae viability, %;
- proportion of diseases, %;
- cocoon weight, %;
- cocoon shell weight, mg;
- percent cocoon shell, %;
- cocoon yield from 1 box of seeds, kg;

- cocoon shell yield from 1 box of seeds, kg;
- key technological parameters.

Based on the above economic indicators, conclusions were made about the adaptability of Chinese hybrids.

Results of the study and their discussion. The article presents the results of the experiment conducted at the Research Institute of Sericulture. For this purpose, the entire infrastructure for breeding larvae was prepared, preparatory works were organized and tests were carried out under optimal conditions. These breeding experiments began primarily with determining the hatchability of foreign and local hybrids.

During the comparative study, the following characteristics were analyzed and calculated: egg hatching, larvae viability, and the proportion of larvae that were healthy at the larval instar but died at the cocoon mounting stage. The results obtained are presented in Table 1.

Table-1

Hatchability of seeds of foreign and local hybrids, larvae viability (2022-2023)

Hybrids	Years	Eggs hatchability, %	Larvae viability, %	Degree of morbidity, %
Parvoz 1 x Foreign	2022	88,7±0,3	95,7±2,5	0,44±0,5
	2023	87,0±0,58	91,8±3,9	4,63±2,36
Parvoz 2 x Foreign	2022	86,3±3,2	92,5±3,1	4,1±1,6
	2023	94,3±0,88	92,1±1,1	5,23±0,81
Pure Foreign Hybrid	2022	87,7±2,6	90,5±3,4	3,04±1,3
	2023	98,7±0,33	95,6±2,6	1,67±0,43
Hybrids imported from China for the spring season				
Foreign hybrid (Q)	2023	99,3±0,67	97,8±0,27	1,33±0,35
Foreign hybrid (K)	2023	99,3±0,33	94,1±1,62	2,3±1,05
Foreign hybrid (M)	2023	92,3±0,33	91,8±1,74	3,5±0,71
Uzbekiston 5 (control)	2022	79,0±1,6	90,8±3,2	2,6±0,6
	2023	96,0±0,58	90,19±2,54	3,63±0,67

The hatchability rate of our local hybrids was 86.3–94.3%. The highest result was shown by Parvoz 2 x Foreign hybrid in 2022. If the degree of eggs hatchability of foreign hybrids was lower in 2022, it became very high in 2023, that is, it amounted to 98.7%.

For the second year of the project, seeds of three new industrial hybrids were imported from China, which were grown and tested at the Research Institute of Sericulture. According to the results obtained, the hybrids named “Q” and “K” showed an extremely high hatchability rate of 99.3%. The viability of larvae was also significantly higher in these two hybrids (97.8% and 94.1%).

The viability of larvae during the cocoon mounting period is high in all hybrids, fully meeting production requirements.

The cocoon productivity index is very important for hybrids, especially because it shows how well hybrids imported from abroad adapt to a given region. The data obtained in this direction are presented in Table 2.

Table-2

Productivity of cocoons of foreign and local hybrids (2022-2023)

Hybrids	Years	Cocoon weight, g	Cocoon shell weight, mg	Percent cocoon shell, %
Parvoz 1 x Foreign	2022	1,92±0,02	417±0,005	21,7±0,22
	2023	2,04±0,03	443±7,89	21,8±0,44
Parvoz 2 x Foreign	2022	1,67±0,02	351±6,0	21,0±0,2
	2023	2,04±0,03	437±9,4	21,5±0,29
Foreign hybrid	2022	1,67±0,02	351±6,0	21,0±0,2
	2023	1,75±0,01	387±7,2	22,0±0,27
Hybrids imported from China for the spring season				
Foreign hybrid (Q)	2023	1,74±0,021	382±5,8	21,8±0,29
Foreign hybrid (K)	2023	1,88±1,06	416±4,04	22,06±0,26
Foreign hybrid (M)	2023	1,98±0,01	445±3,21	22,4±0,10
Uzbekistan 5 (control)	2022	2,16±0,04	452±9,5	20,9±0,8
	2023	2,55±0,03	536±11,3	21,0±0,26

The weight of cocoons obtained from our local hybrids averaged 1.67–2.04 g. Hybrid Uzbekistan 5, taken as a control, had a cocoon weight of 2.16 to 2.55 g, which is a higher result than that of foreign hybrids.

As noted above, when analyzing the cocoon productivity of three hybrids imported from China for testing in 2023, the weight of cocoons obtained from these three hybrids was 1.74-1.98 g, and their percent cocoon shell was within 21.8-22.4%. When compared with previous breeds and hybrids, it turned out that the hybrids called “Q”, “K” and “M” have significantly higher indicators.

Also, within the framework of the joint project, 8 types of industrial hybrids were presented for the 2024 season (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Industrial hybrid seeds imported from China.

All biological materials have undergone comprehensive testing in specialized worm farms of the Research Institute of Sericulture, and their key economic indicators, such as egg hatchability, larvae viability, and cocoon productivity have been determined. Table 3 presents these indicators.

Table-3

Key economic indicators of rare hybrids imported from China (2024)

Hybrids	Eggs hatchability, %	Larvae viability, %	Degree of morbidity, %	Cocoon weight,	Percent cocoon shell, %
“2306008”	97,7	88,0	3,8	1,97	21,5
“2710”	98,7	92,0	2,2	2,11	23,4
“2120”	95,0	96,7	0,7	1,82	23,6
“2309012”	99,3	90,7	2,2	2,05	22,0
“2306087”	99,7	90,0	2,6	2,10	22,0
“6516”	99,7	93,3	1,8	1,72	20,7
“2309013”	98,2	94,7	2,1	2,09	22,0
“6316”	97,8	93,0	2,2	1,70	21,0

From the data in Table 3, we can conclude that it is worth separately noting the new hybrids imported from China, since these 8 hybrid combinations have proven themselves very well in the conditions of Uzbekistan and have shown high results. In particular, the hatchability of eggs fluctuated within the range of 95.0–99.7%. The viability of larvae also showed a fairly high result – 88.0–94.7%. These figures show the suitability of the new hybrids for our conditions. Almost all new hybrids showed high cocoon weight indexes, and the heaviest cocoons were in hybrid No. 2710 – 2.11 g. The percent cocoon shell was also at the required level and amounted to 20.7–23.6%.

Our joint experiments in this direction have shown that among the new hybrids imported from China, it is possible to select forms that will produce a high yield of cocoons and high-quality silk also in the conditions of Uzbekistan. It is planned to carry out extensive selection work on these breeds in the next generations.

Conclusions. The viability indicators of hybrids involving Uzbek and Chinese breeds are noteworthy – 91.8–95.7% and 86.3–94.3%. The morbidity rate of foreign hybrids was minimal and amounted to 0.57–3.3% and 1.57–2.13%, respectively, and the indicators of other breeding material were also at the required level.

The most important characteristics are the weight and percent cocoon shell. Based on the results of our research, we can conclude that, first of all, hybrid seeds imported from China to Uzbekistan have many positive characteristics in terms of high seed hatchability and leading technological parameters. Based on the results of preliminary studies, it became clear that these hybrids need to be provided with optimal conditions to fully reveal their genetic potential in the conditions of Uzbekistan. This conclusion is of great importance for increasing the yield of cocoons obtained from 1 box of these hybrids larvae. Also, for the purpose of rational use of Chinese hybrids in the future, while maintaining their high technological characteristics, it is advisable to carry out selection work with the participation of Uzbek breeds and create crossbreeds and hybrids suitable for the conditions of Uzbekistan.

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